

SCALED EM

Scaling Democratic Innovations: Emerging Practices for Future Policies /D1.2 Policy Report

WP 1, T 1.3

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Executive Summary

This Policy Report supports policymakers and practitioners seeking to **scale democratic innovations (DIs)** to make them lasting and impactful. It addresses two guiding questions:

- What foundations are needed for a practical theory of scaling democratic innovations?
- How do impediments and enablers to scaling relate to variations in DI performance to succeed?

The analysis builds on two earlier milestones of the ScaleDem project:

- A living **Knowledge Map** (currently 100 entries) that classifies cases of democratic innovation by type and scaling potential, and
- An **Analytical Framework** that defines four dimensions of scaling (out, in, deep, and high).

Using these resources, we applied a first **Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA)** to a sample of 60 cases from the Knowledge Map. The goal was to identify how overall performance varies depending on scaling potentials and the enablers through which innovations scale across the four dimensions mentioned above.

The report proceeds in five steps:

1. **Framing the challenge:** We highlight the knowledge–practice gap in achieving impactful democratic innovations and explain why a grounded, practical theory of scaling is required.
2. **Data foundations:** We present the CORDIS and other sources on which the dynamic Knowledge Map is built, forming the basis for systematic comparison.
3. **Comparative analysis:** We share findings from the first QCA, focusing on how variations in scaling conditions affect DI performance across a medium-sized sample of 60 cases.
4. **Early lessons:** Drawing on the Knowledge Map and QCA, we identify three sets of cases from “pathbreakers”, “pioneers”, and “path-testers” from which different kinds of lessons can be drawn—elements for theorizing conditions and constraints for scaling solutions, experiments, and critical reflections.
5. **Conclusions, Next steps, Key Messages:** outlines open questions, gaps, and future directions for connecting research and practice.

1. Bridging the Knowledge-Practice Gap

"Nothing is as practical as a good theory." – Kurt Lewin

1.1 The Challenge: A Grounded Scaling Theory for Changing Practices

Scaling democratic innovations (DIs) is one of today's key challenges for strengthening democracy's resilience and responsiveness. From local participatory budgeting to transnational citizens' assemblies, many promising ideas, experiments, and pilots remain isolated or short-lived practices.

Following Glaser & Strauss (1967), "grounded theory" was initially conceived to generate theory from empirical data. Grounded theorizing of scaling DIs should help us understand how such innovations may scale, from one-off experimentations to lasting practices.

Indeed, scaling democratic innovations means more than simply making them bigger. It describes the process of how practices move beyond isolated pilots to become more **embedded, resilient, and impactful**. The [ScaleDem analytical framework](#) identifies **four scaling dimensions**, each pointing to a different way innovations grow and gain meaning: **out, high, deep, and in**.

- **Out:** spreading to more places and reaching more people
- **High:** gaining political and institutional buy-in
- **Deep:** embedding in mainstream culture and values
- **In:** improving quality and standards

By contrast, "practical theorizing" aims at generating theory not FROM but FOR practical action. It is a reflexive practice and co-production between researchers and practitioners. It is also empirically grounded, not just in real-world challenges and experiences, but in concrete, actionable tools for making democracy more inclusive, deliberative, and impactful.

To be of practical use, a theory of scaling might seek to identify **principles that can be reused and adapted to different local, regional, or national contexts. It might develop readiness checks and learning infrastructures** that allow innovations to scale without losing their core values. Such a theory would aim to provide researchers, practitioners, and policymakers with a framework that shows **what works where, and why**—and that guides action, not just reflection.

In Lewin's spirit, we see democracy as both a subject of analysis and change. To bridge the knowledge-action gap, this Policy Report considers both complementary: grounded theory provides the evidence that practical theorizing would seek to make actionable in lived contexts. By learning from past experiences, ScaleDem draws lessons for future action. We aim to offer researchers, policymakers, and practitioners a **shared foundation** for jointly developing a practical theory of scaling that can help democratic practices grow **high and deep, in and out**.

1.2 Is One General Theory Enough? Families of Democratic Innovations

Democratic innovations are solutions to improve how citizens engage with and influence decision-making. They aim to make governance more inclusive, legitimate, and responsive—whether through participatory budgeting at the local level, transnational citizens’ assemblies, or digital platforms for civic input.

While it is helpful to look for common patterns, one single theory of scaling cannot capture their diversity. Scaling a digital tool differs from scaling a local assembly or reforming an electoral law. The latter requires broad public debates and cultural norm shifts. Institutionalizing citizen assemblies, or lowering the voting age at 16 (scaling ‘high’) does not mean that it automatically gets accepted by the general population (scaling ‘deep’) Similarly, digital tools can technically be replicated from local to national (scaling ‘out’), but scaling them ‘deep’ requires norm changes solutions to overcome trust issues, digital divides etc.

Each innovative solution works in a different setting, with different goals, actors, and constraints. That is why any general framework should leave room for specific pathways to reflect the various logics of families of democratic innovations (see Appendix A.1):

- **Administrative:** improving how public administrations and institutions work.
- **Deliberative:** creating structured spaces for inclusive and informed discussion.
- **Digital & AI-based:** using technology to widen participation and navigate complexity.
- **Direct:** giving citizens binding decision-making power, e.g., referenda.
- **Electoral:** reforming how representatives are chosen and held accountable.
- **Participatory:** engaging citizens directly in shaping policies, plans, and budgets.

Taken together, these families show the diversity of today’s democratic innovation ecosystem. They highlight why scaling cannot be explained by one general theory but requires family-specific insights that capture how innovations spread, gain legitimacy, and endure.

1.3 Overview of the Report and Early Findings

This Policy Report proceeds in five steps:

1. **Framing the challenge:** We highlight the knowledge–practice gap in achieving scalable democratic innovations and explain why a grounded, practical theory of scaling is required.
2. **Data foundations:** We present the CORDIS and other sources on which the dynamic Knowledge Map is built, forming the basis for systematic comparison.
3. **Comparative analysis:** We share findings from the first QCA, focusing on how variations in scaling conditions affect DI performance across a medium-sized sample of 60 cases.
4. **Early lessons:** Drawing on the Knowledge Map and QCA, we identify three kinds of lessons - from “pathbreakers”, “pioneers” and “path-testers”, with lists of cases and selected illustrations:

5. **Conclusions, next steps, and key messages:** summarizing open questions, gaps, and future directions for research and practice.

These findings reflect the first ten months of ScaleDem research on how to scale DIs and remain preliminary. Over the course of the project, we will expand the Knowledge Map to around 300 cases and complement QCA with additional methods, including process-tracing, interviews with policymakers and stakeholders, and analysis of media and citizen perspectives. This multimethod approach will provide deeper insights, address potential biases, and strengthen the evidence base.

The forthcoming **Deliverable D1.3 (due at Month 24)** will therefore present a more robust account of the conditions that enable democratic innovations to scale in ways that are not only sustainable but also resilient—and potentially transformative. This Policy Report is an intermediary step to spark discussions and build a consolidated theory of scaling democratic innovations with the community of actors active in the DIs field.

2. Empirical Grounds for a Theory of Scaling Democratic Innovations

To understand the scalability potentials and outcomes of democratic innovations, QCA provides an empirically grounded methodology. For ScaleDem, it is grounded in the cases gathered in the [ScaleDem Knowledge Map \(M1\)](#), and analytically structured by the categories set out in the [ScaleDem Analytical Framework \(D1.1\)](#). The QCA method is widely used in business studies,¹ international relations,² and political science, among others. It has already been used to assess democratic innovation practices, such as participatory budgeting.³

This section provides an overview of three connected stepping stones towards a theory of scaling: the ScaleDem Knowledge Map, Data Coding, and the QCA Model Design.

2.1. The Living ScaleDem Knowledge Map

We use open-access databases, primarily CORDIS, complemented by Participedia and other data repositories to build a grounded Knowledge Map. At present, our living ScaleDem Knowledge Map provides entries for 70 democratic innovations that we have identified from past and ongoing projects documented by the [Cordis database](#) (funded under the Horizon H2020 and HEU, FP7, ERC, MSCA programs), supplemented by other sources. For each case counted as a democratic innovation with relevant scaling potentials, a basic “summary” is drafted, stored in the online [Zotero](#) library, and embedded in the Knowledge Map.⁴

Each summary includes the flagship DI cases per project⁵ for in-depth analysis (as well as project acronym, full title, and duration; information on DI cases and scaling potentials; link to online repository). From the 70 initial cases, we could find enough information to run a proper qualitative comparative analysis on 61 cases. For the sake of simplicity, this report refers to these cases of DI through the project's codename (Acronym). The characteristics of each case can be found in the case summaries of each project in our [Knowledge Map](#). Additionally, the cases were organized according to their scaling potentials and family(ies) of DI (see Appendix A.2.1).

¹ Fainshmidt, Stav, Michael A. Witt, Ruth V. Aguilera, and Alain Verbeke. "The contributions of qualitative comparative analysis (QCA) to international business research." *Journal of international business studies* 51, no. 4 (2020): 455-466.

² Bara, Corinne. "Incentives and opportunities: A complexity-oriented explanation of violent ethnic conflict." *Journal of Peace Research* 51, no. 6 (2014): 696-710.

³ Ryan, Matt. *Why citizen participation succeeds or fails: a comparative analysis of participatory budgeting*. Policy Press, 2021.

⁴ The relevant cases that have not yet been included in the present analysis will be analyzed subsequently, when all data is gathered.

⁵ Except for the project Scalable Democracy, from which we selected two cases.

2.2 Data Coding for Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA)

Each case was analyzed qualitatively using an analytical [template](#) with 15 items, which EUSurvey hosts. These items report information on the case through a modular framework built inductively from the information available on cases and inspired by the [Democratic Odyssey framework](#). The corresponding project information was used as a proxy for items where case-specific information was unavailable (such as *Duration* and *Financing*). The data for other items was gathered through project document analysis (on items such as *Membership*, *Political Buy-in*, and *Stage of Research and Development*) and through interpretative analysis on more complex items (such as *Problem Solution* and *Evaluation*, among others). This produced over 250 pages of information on the 61 cases.

In the next step, these data were coded by categories derived from the cases themselves (inductively) and the [Analytical Framework](#) (deductively). This aimed at minimizing the wealth of qualitative information to essential information fitting an Excel datasheet. Minimizing required the creation of categories that captured the characteristics of all cases, and, at the same time, helped build a **Grounded Model** for QCA.

2.3 Designing a Grounded QCA Model

We use Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) to develop a grounded theory of scaling DIs. Given the high complexity of the scaling dimensions, each comprising different sub-dimensions, and components (see D1.1), we want to compare across a relatively high number of cases of democratic innovations the *configurational* relations between different sets of conditions (the dimensions of scaling) and varying outcomes, that is the overall performance of a democratic innovation regarding its duration, geographical wide spread, status (from an idea or blueprint over a single or iterative pilot, to regular practice or institutionalization).

QCA helps practitioners and researchers gain a nuanced understanding of complex phenomena by considering the interplay of various factors within different cases. The QCA research method is used to study how different combinations of conditions lead to varying outcomes. Instead of looking at single causes in isolation, it focuses on patterns and pathways across cases to see which conditions, when combined, are linked to success or failure.⁶ It is especially useful for policy research with small to medium numbers of cases, where statistical methods may not work well, and when qualitative variables are too complex to be reduced to quantitative proxies. Instead of looking at single causes in isolation, QCA focuses on patterns and pathways across cases to see which conditions, when combined, are linked to success or failure.

⁶ Oana, Ioana-Elena, Carsten Q. Schneider, and Eva Thomann. *Qualitative comparative analysis using R: A beginner's guide*. Cambridge University Press, 2021; Wagemann, Claudius. "Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) and set theory." In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Politics*. 2017; Mello, Patrick A. "Qualitative comparative analysis." In *Routledge Handbook of Foreign Policy Analysis Methods*, pp. 385-402. Routledge, 2022.

Depending on the fit of the QCA-Model with the collected data, it can serve as a building block for our prospective Theory of Scaling: For the scope of our research, this Model is structured by three meta-categories: “Scope Conditions”, “Scaling Dimensions”, and “Outcomes” of DI Cases. Each of them comprises a set of empirical indicators, formulated as questions.

Our QCA model consists of four explanatory conditions (the four dimensions of scaling) and the outcome (performance of the DI). We also test three scope conditions (*Family of DI*, *Geographical Scope*, and *Governance Scope*). The scaling dimensions are operationalized through questions that can be found in Appendix A.2.2, the answers to which are tagged by specific values.

In response to each of these questions, a brief text was formulated and then transformed into a value according to different categories of answers. These values were then aggregated for each condition (dimension of scaling) through a weighted algorithm. The values, weights, and corresponding case template items can be found in the [dataset](#).

Together as pathways, knowledge about the combinations of scaling potentials and their outcomes helps generate a more **comprehensive guide to scaling** DIs than simple linear growth models.

3. First Comparative Findings: Unpacking DI Performance and Scaling Pathways

Based on the 60 selected cases and the empirical operationalizations for the QCA model described above, this section presents the preliminary results of this first QCA analysis.

3.1 Pathways Toward Transformative Performance

The analysis of the 61 DI cases confirms that scaling is rarely the result of a single factor. Instead, it depends on the right combination of strategies that are in sync with the case's context conditions. Where these ingredients are present, cases are far more likely to grow, embed, and endure. Where they are missing, promising ideas often fail to take root. The QCA reveals two possibly sufficient "recipes", or "mix of ingredients" (what we refer to below as "scaling pathways"), each showing a different combination of strategies to scale a DI.

Pathway 1. Scaling Out + Scaling High + Scaling In:

This includes cases that spread geographically or included a high number of citizens (scaling out), gained formal political or legal backing (scaling high), and improved their quality and integration into governance systems (scaling in). The cases analyzed that follow this pathway include DIs developed in CIMULACT, CIVITAS ReVeAL, DEMOCRAT, DEMOTEC, EUARENAS, iDEM, NEBourhoods, ORBIS, PentaHelix, PHOENIX, REAL DEAL, and WeGovNow.

Pathway 2. Scaling Out + Scaling Deep + Scaling In:

This includes cases that spread geographically or included a high number of citizens, strengthened internal quality (scaling in), and fostered cultural change and civic norms, making participation part of everyday life (scaling deep). The cases analyzed that follow this pathway include DIs developed in CCINDLE, Co-Inform, CO-SUSTAIN, CRITICAL CHANGELAB, DO, ENLIGHTENMe, INVOLVE, MultiPoD, DEMOCRAT, DEMOTEC, EUARENAS, iDEM, NEBourhoods, ORBIS, PentaHelix, PHOENIX, REAL DEAL, and WeGovNow.

Dual Pathways. 1 + 2:

Several cases⁷ appeared in both lists. These "dual-pathway cases" are particularly valuable for learning, as they achieve both institutional anchoring and cultural embedding. Follow-up case studies are now needed to understand the conditions under which successful scaling takes place, and the tools by which some case designs may successfully combine both pathways.

⁷ The ones in the projects DEMOCRAT, DEMOTEC, EUARENAS, iDEM, NEBourhoods, ORBIS, PentaHelix, PHOENIX, REAL DEAL, and WeGovNow.

Figure 1 “Overlapping Scaling Pathways” shows the two main combinations of scaling strategies that have led to relatively longer-lived—or even lasting—impact in our analysis of 61 DI cases.⁸ In both pathways, cases expanded geographically and numerically (scaling out) and strengthened their quality and integration into governance systems (scaling in). The third ingredient varied: some succeeded by gaining formal institutional support (scaling high), while others achieved profound cultural change (scaling deep).

Figure 1. *Overlapping Scaling Pathways*

3.2 Mapping DI Scaling Potentials and Outcomes

The Performance Map in Figure 2 places each case relative to the success patterns identified in our analysis. Cases in the upper right followed combinations of scaling strategies that consistently performed well. Those in other quadrants either lacked one or more key elements or applied them

⁸ For an explanation of the different categories of performance and its relationship to success as an outcome, please see Appendix A.3.1.

less effectively. This visualization helps identify which cases can serve as strong models for replication and which could benefit from redesign before scaling further.⁹

Figure 2. Performance Map

Note. In QCA terms, this is a sufficiency plot for the presence of the outcome (performance). See the [Annex](#) for the technical names of the case types and explanations.

Depending on their performance, the individual cases can be organized by four different quadrants according to their performance and scaling potentials:

- **Quadrant I. "Strong Performers"**: Cases that achieved the outcome and had the right success factors in place ("typical cases"). These are our best role models; they show how the right conditions can lead to successful scaling.
- **Quadrant II. "Unexpected Wins"**: Deviant coverage cases that succeeded despite not having all the expected success factors. These "surprise successes" are worth studying to see what other factors might explain their results.
- **Quadrant III. "Low Priority"**: Cases that neither had the success factors nor scaled. These tell us little about how scaling works, and as such, fall outside the learning scope of ScaleDem.
- **Quadrant IV. "Missed Opportunities"**: Cases with success factors in place but did not scale. These are especially interesting to compare with Quadrant I; they can reveal hidden barriers or missing pieces, and are interesting cases to include for ScaleDem's upcoming bittersweet lessons series.

⁹ Because the sample size is still relatively small, this analysis will be revisited when more cases are available.

Finally, there is the question of how consistently the success factors vary across DI families, European regions, and levels of governance. Table 1 shows how the two scaling pathways presented above performed across different categories of cases. The performance was calculated by testing the pathways across various contexts, looking for differences that could indicate contextual obstacles and enablers to be further explored. See the [Annex](#) for more information on the calculations.

Table 1. Model Performance in Diverse Contexts

DI Families	Scope Conditions	
	Regions of the EU	Project Level
Conditions: Administrative and/or electoral; Direct and/or digital; Participatory and/or deliberative	Conditions: Eastern; Northern; Southern; and Western Europe	Conditions: EU multilevel; Multinational and compared national; National or subnational; Transnational or translocal

The model performs consistently across project types. Model performance is somewhat lower in Southern Europe, suggesting the need for further research and potential targeted support. EU multilevel and transnational projects tend to show a higher level of consistency.

3.3 Paths towards Selective Performance

Looking for necessary pathways (as opposed to sufficient) for DI performance, our QCA has not yet yielded significant results (see the [Annex](#) for more details). However, the results show that the not-so-highly successful projects usually face a common set of barriers.

The table in Appendix A.3.2 shows examples of cases that share the same main scaling gaps, such as missing geographic spread (scaling out), weak institutional anchoring (scaling high), or a lack of cultural change (scaling deep). The cases lacking geographic spread and profound cultural change (~OUT + ~DEEP), or those lacking geographic spread and internal quality improvements (~OUT + ~IN), were often unsuccessful. The same pattern appeared for cases missing institutional embedding and profound cultural change (~HIGH + ~DEEP) or institutional embedding and internal quality improvements (~HIGH + ~IN).

These combinations may point to deeper, underlying problems—such as weak overall design or lack of long-term vision—but more research is needed to confirm this, as is pointed out below on our next steps. The QCA suggests that two cases are worth looking at more closely to understand these patterns in scaling gaps: KT4D (typical for missing both spread and cultural change) and DEMOS-ACT (typical for all four missing-dimension combinations; see section 4.3 for a detailed description).

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The QCA results above confirm that there is no one-size-fits-all route to scaling democratic innovations; instead, success comes from different combinations of factors depending on the context. The goal now is to turn to recommendations about what we can learn from the emerging practices we have analyzed so far for future strategies.

4. Early Lessons from Pathbreakers, Pioneers, and Path-Testers

This section combines lessons from the Knowledge Map and QCA to propose strategies for designing the future ScaleDem Scaling Grounds (i.e., pilot and twinning actions). Moreover, it provides the first recommendations for project designers, practitioners, and policymakers. They highlight core challenges, successful coping strategies, and “bittersweet lessons” from past experiences.

The lessons can be grouped into three clusters:

- Lessons from **Pathbreakers** are about what it takes to innovate: how to push boundaries, try out bold designs, risk-taking, and experimentation, to open new opportunities, even if outcomes remain uncertain. Their lessons are less about stability than how to disrupt, overcome resistance, open new pathways, and generate momentum for follow-up initiatives, spin-offs extending the innovation beyond its origin.
- Lessons from **Pioneers** address what it takes to last—for instance, consolidation, endurance, and transferability rather than novelty, where democratic innovations have already taken root and show staying power, demonstrating how to safeguard, for instance, against political cycles, shifting priorities, or hostile actors.
- Lessons from early-stage **Path-Testers** teach the value of failure—hence projects that have tried something new and stumbled, but left behind valuable learning. Their lessons are neither about consolidation nor breakthroughs but about what not to repeat, what to adapt, how to clarify feasibility checks, re-design pitfalls, and adapt to context sensitivity. The value of failure lies in engaging constructively with these trials and errors that provide critical learning.

To illustrate these different lessons, the ScaleDem Knowledge-Map and QCA findings provide project cases with lessons that can contribute directly to developing a grounded theory of scaling for changing democratic practices.

4.1 Pathbreakers for Scaling Out, Deep, High, or In

Drawing on qualitative insights from the ScaleDem Knowledge Map and QCA, an extensive range of pilots illustrate what it takes to open up opportunities for new pathways, at the cost of risk-taking and experimentation under constraints of resistances and barriers (see Appendices A.4, A.4.1, A.4.2, A.4.3, and A.4.4 for a detailed list). Here are four examples of such pilots:

Pilot 1. DEMOCRAT: Combining Expansion with Embedding

Geographic spread works best when paired with either institutional anchoring or cultural change. In DEMOCRAT, replication across diverse contexts succeeded when elite support ensured policy uptake and when a compelling narrative of citizen empowerment reinforced legitimacy.

Pilot 2. CIVITAS ReVeAL: Securing Political and Community Buy-In

Early and sustained engagement of policymakers and local stakeholders increases chances of success. In Vitoria Gasteiz, Spain, CIVITAS ReVeAL's "urban superblock" design improved citizens' quality of life, but only because officials actively co-participated in planning and implementation.

Pilot 3. [REAL DEAL](#): Maintaining Process Quality

High-quality processes safeguard legitimacy. REAL DEAL strengthened its deliberations by co-organizing formats with CSOs, running ex-post workshops, developing protocols, toolkits, and even a feminist moderation course, and building capacities within civil society. These efforts are to scale in sustained credibility and impact.

Pilot 4. [ORBIS](#): Leveraging Multilevel Settings

Projects that link local, regional, national, and EU levels benefit from visibility and feedback loops. ORBIS demonstrated how iteration across governance levels improved process quality and reinforced positive results.

Further in-depth research (e.g., interviews with coordinators and policymakers) into these and more cases is needed to understand these patterns fully.

4.2 Pioneers for Twinning Communities

For twinning designers and implementers, several CORDIS and Participedia cases stand out as showcases for endurance and transferability across diverse contexts:

- [EUARENAS](#). Multiple iterations of assemblies and forums across Estonia, Poland, Hungary, and Italy addressed the citizen-politics disconnect, making it a model for scaling out in diverse contexts.
- [Critical ChangeLab](#). This project exemplifies structured scaling by creating youth-led "labs" in 10 countries with explicit narratives and tested protocols.
- [Democratic Odyssey](#). Its travelling citizens' assemblies' model and modular framework demonstrate strong potential for scaling out and twinning.

Additional promising cases include:

- [PentaHelix](#): A multi-stakeholder climate action method now tested in NetZeroCities.
- [EnlightenME](#): Urban Lighting Labs co-created with citizens and caregivers.
- [NEBourhoods](#): A wide-ranging regeneration model in Munich with strong replication potential.
- [PHOENIX](#): Adaptable pilots tailored to Green Deal challenges across governance levels.
- [DEMOTEC](#): Participatory budgeting pilots in seven cities, producing frameworks and manuals for replication.

4.3 Path-Testers: “Bittersweet Lessons” for Critical Learning

- [GenderQuotas](#) – Focused mainly on Albania, the project generated insights into women’s roles in low-quality democracies but lacked replicability in other contexts. Despite a small budget, its results remain a valuable foundation for future DIs.
- [REBALANCE](#) – Explored future trends in transport and mobility, but excluded citizen participation and lacked policy protocols. This limited the democratic quality of its outputs, weakening otherwise promising policy proposals.
- [ITHACA](#) – Created a vast archive of migrant and refugee narratives, highlighting their voices in governance. Yet without elite or policymaker support, the results had little policy resonance despite their cultural and social value.
- [IDEalreSCUE](#) – Produced a sophisticated resilience framework and urban modelling tool for emergencies. However, the absence of policymaker uptake left its strong technical results without practical application.
- [KT4D](#) – Advanced a tech-enabled vision of democracy through digital tools, but lacked a compelling citizen-oriented narrative. This weakens its capacity to scale deeply into democratic culture, despite ongoing work.
- [DEMOS-ACT](#) – Offered a systematic analysis of European democratic innovations and built a theoretical framework. Yet by stopping at the analytical level without a citizen-facing narrative, it struggled to generate scaling potential.

Regional disparities, governance levels, and policy domains all matter. To address these conditions, ScaleDem wants to engage policymakers and practitioners directly in co-developing “bitter-sweet lessons” from past experiences for a more robust grounded theory of scaling. This will complement the ScaleDem Knowledge Map and QCA with lived experience.

4.4 Recommendations at a Glance

Before turning to the conclusion and next steps, this section presents our first recommendations to the DI community of practice.

For Policymakers

- Support dual-path scaling: fund initiatives combining spread with institutional embedding or cultural change.
- Require scaling plans as part of funding and evaluation criteria.
- Tailor funding and support to address regional disparities.

For Practitioners

- Design pilots with built-in scaling strategies (out, high, deep, in).
- Use twinning and mentoring to adapt and exchange methods across contexts.
- Document lessons and produce toolkits or protocols for replication.

For the R&I Community

- Prioritize comparative and longitudinal studies of scaling pathways.

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- Refine indicators for scaling deep (cultural change) and scaling in (quality).
- Facilitate partnerships between practitioners and researchers to co-create knowledge.

Design Principles for Future Pilots & Twinings

- Build for integration from the start: Plan how initiatives fit into governance systems.
- Adapt for local fit: Twinning is not cloning, so allow local flexibility.
- Invest in relationships: Sustained engagement with policymakers and communities builds legitimacy.
- Track and learn: Monitor continuously to refine strategies before scaling further.

5. Conclusions, Next Steps & Key Messages

In conclusion, we outline open theoretical questions, knowledge gaps, and future directions for connecting research and practice.

This report has highlighted how scaling democratic innovations depends on the interaction of enabling and constraining conditions. While some cases demonstrate strong performance outcomes when scaling pathways are aligned with supportive institutional, cultural, and political contexts, others face persistent barriers that limit their reach or sustainability. The key theoretical challenge is to better understand these impediments—such as institutional resistance, limited resources, or fragmented participation—and the enabling factors that allow innovations to embed and endure. Addressing these questions is crucial for designing policies and practices that transform pilot projects into resilient, impactful democratic innovations.

Our initial QCA has generated valuable insights into how scaling conditions shape performance, but it also has limitations. QCA identifies configurations across cases but does not capture the deeper processes, narratives, and contextual dynamics that influence outcomes. To close these blind spots, ScaleDem will integrate complementary methods such as process-tracing, interviews with policymakers and practitioners, and analyzing media and citizen perspectives. This multimethod approach will allow us to validate patterns identified through QCA, uncover overlooked causal mechanisms, and provide richer, practice-oriented lessons for scaling democratic innovations.

5.1 Next Steps

Looking ahead, ScaleDem will expand the Knowledge Map from the current 100 cases to approximately 300, offering a far more comprehensive foundation for comparative analysis. This enlarged dataset will enhance the robustness of QCA and allow for systematic testing of diverse scaling pathways across different families of democratic innovation. Combined with the multimethod approach, the expanded Knowledge Map will strengthen the evidence base for policymakers and practitioners. It will also lay the groundwork for a more consolidated theory of scaling—one that explains not only how democratic innovations spread, but also how they can become lasting, resilient, and transformative.

5.2 Summary of Key Messages

- **Scaling requires both enablers and safeguards.** Lasting democratic innovations depend on supportive institutional, political, and cultural contexts and strategies to overcome barriers.
- **QCA is powerful but insufficient to understand the dynamics behind these patterns fully.** Qualitative comparative analysis reveals scaling patterns, yet deeper processes and contexts must be understood through complementary methods.

- **A multimethod approach strengthens evidence.** Combining QCA with process-tracing, based on interviews, focus groups, surveys of policymakers and stakeholders, civil society, and media analysis, will uncover causal mechanisms and close blind spots.
- **The Knowledge Map is expanding.** Growing from 100 to ~300 cases, it will provide a stronger foundation for testing scaling pathways across all families of democratic innovations.
- **Toward a consolidated theory of scaling.** Evidence from these diverse grounds will guide policymakers and practitioners in transforming pilots into resilient, impactful, and potentially transformative democratic innovations.

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Appendices

A.1. Six DI Families Compared (Elstub & Escobar's Framework, 2019)

Family *)	Core Focus *)	Purpose of Innovation	Stage of Policy Cycle	Institutionalization target	Initiators / Sponsorship	Inclusiveness / Access	Use of Technological Tools
Administrative	Institutional procedures, bureaucratic responsiveness, and co-governance mechanisms	Transparency, accountability, efficiency, trust in institutions	Downstream (implementation, monitoring)	High (inside government structures)	Top-down (public administrators, elected officials)	Selective (civil servants, stakeholders, experts, organized civil society)	Limited (feedback, dashboards, e-gov tools)
Deliberative	Structured discussion, informed reasoning, and collective judgment	Legitimacy, mutual understanding, collective reasoning	Upstream to midstream (agenda-setting, recommendation)	Medium to low (often ad hoc or consultative)	Mixed (governments, CSOs, researchers, foundations)	High (usually random selection, inclusivity by design)	Medium (deliberation platforms, online forums)
Digital- & AI-Based	Technology-enabled and AI-assisted tools for	Inclusion, personalization, resilience against	Cross-stage (from agenda-setting to monitoring)	Variable (pilot projects to institutional platforms)	Mixed (civic tech developers,	High (wide outreach;)	Central (digital platforms, AI

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	engagement, verification, and decision-making	disinformation, assistance			public institutions)		tools, algorithms)
Direct	Citizens making binding decisions on laws, policies, or constitutional matters	Universal Citizen empowerment, legal control over decision-making	Midstream (decision-making via referenda, initiatives)	High (requires constitutional/legal frameworks)	Mostly top-down (legislatures); sometimes citizen-driven within legal frameworks	Very High (open to all eligible voters)	Varies, e-voting, info portals, campaign tech)
Electoral	Reforming how representatives are chosen and held accountable	Fairness, inclusivity, representativeness, and electoral integrity	Midstream (selection of representatives)	High (core democratic institutions)	Top-down (electoral commissions, parties, legislators)	Very High (all eligible voters)	Moderate (electronic voting, auditing systems)
Participatory	Citizens contributing to decisions, planning, and implementation through inclusive formats	Empowerment, civic learning, and co-creation of public goods	Upstream to downstream (planning, budgeting, implementation)	Medium (depends on local integration into governance)	Often bottom-up (CSOs, communities, local governments)	Selective (residents, local communities, often underrepresented groups)	Moderate to high (digital mapping, participatory budgeting platforms, hybrid models)

A.2.1. Knowledge Map of 70 Cases, by DI Family and Scaling Potentials

Type/Dimension	Scaling Out	Scaling High	Scaling Deep	Scaling In
Administrative	ACCTING, CMCG, COGOV, NetZeroCities, PERITIA	ActEU, CIMULACT, Co-Val, EU3D, PERITIA, RECONNECT	IDEal reSCUE, PERITIA	CIT-PART, CITADEL, CO3, IMPACT, INVOLVE, TROPICO
Deliberative	DO, G1000, IDEM, InCite-Dem, MultiPoD, PDC, PHOENIX, REAL DEAL, REBALANCE	PDC, Scalable Democracy (2)	AECED, CCINDLE, DO, REAL DEAL, New_Democracy	EUARENAS, IDEM, ORBIS, PHOENIX
Digital	Co-Inform, D-CENT, REDemocracIA, Scalable Democracy (1), vTaiwan	MEDIADELCOM, SMIDGE, REDIRECT, Scalable Democracy (1), WeGovNow	KT4D, REDIRECT, SMIDGE, TITAN	Co-Inform, CO3, ECePS, EUCOMMEET, IDEM, KT4D, MultiPoD
Direct	D-CENT	WYDE, LIDD	DEMOS-ACT	LIDD
Electoral	PACITA, PDC	GenderQuotas, WYDE, CIVICS, PDC, SEEVS	New_Democracy	EU3D, PACITA, SEEVS
Participatory	D-CENT, DEMOTEC, G1000, ISEED, NEBourhoods, NetZeroCities, OBM, PentaHelix, Scalable Democracy (1)	CMCG, DEMOCRAT, DEMOTEC, DII, ITHACA, OPP, Scalable Democracy (1)	Critical ChangeLab, ENCODE, DEMOCRAT, ITHACA	EUARENAS, InCite-Dem

A.2.2. Operationalizing Scaling Dimensions: QCA Measures and Analytical Framework

Dimension	Definition	Sub-Dimensions and Main Components	Operationalization Question
Scaling High	Integration into formal institutions and policymaking (institutional ascent)	<i>Institutional embedding:</i> consolidated structures (permanent staff, stable budgets)	How much public funding did the case receive?
			How much funding from private entities?
		<i>Policy uptake:</i> adoption of innovation outputs into policies or laws	Does the case receive any public endorsement (binding commitment to following up on recommendations; institutional, symbolic; uptake in lobbying, electoral platforms, etc.)?
		<i>Legal embedding:</i> formal rules or mandates (often with mandated follow-up)	
Scaling Out	Expansion across new places, sectors, participants (horizontal, vertical, transversal)	<i>Horizontal:</i> adoption in new locations, institutions, or policy domains	<i>Is the case based on a cross-regional (=North, East, South, West-European) /transnational/translocal iteration?</i>
		<i>Vertical:</i> uptake at higher/lower governance levels (local to national/global)	<i>At which level has the case been developed?</i>
		<i>Transversal:</i> growing number and diversity of participants (including underrepresented groups)	Did the case have mass and/or social media coverage? Which type of deliberative format? (measures the number of participants) Were multipliers like NGOs and others included?
Scaling Deep	Deepening impact on civic values, norms, and identity (culture and engagement)	<i>Performative:</i> increased trust and satisfaction in democracy	Are narratives effectively deployed to embed democratic innovations culturally?
		<i>Normative:</i> stronger belief in democratic values (e.g., deliberation, legitimacy)	Does the case cater to the needs of vulnerable groups, for instance, refugees, jobless or homeless people (among many others), included in the case?

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		<i>Symbolic</i> : participants feel heard and politically recognized	Are civic-participatory arts included in the case for enhancing deliberation?
		<i>Emotional</i> : pride, hope, and belonging from civic engagement	Does the case aim at active democratic citizenship? (e.g., individual or collective action of some sort, petitions, tools for protecting rights, fighting disinformation, etc.)
		<i>Behavioral</i> : continued civic participation after the initial innovation	
Scaling In	Enhancing internal process quality and sustainability	<p><i>Inclusiveness</i>: equal voice and support for all participants throughout the process</p> <p><i>Process integrity</i>: transparent, fair, well-structured procedures (clear rules, respectful dialogue)</p> <p><i>Effectiveness</i>: clear agendas, coherent process, and tangible outcomes (recommendations/decisions)</p> <p><i>Learning/feedback</i>: evaluation, adaptation, and continual improvement</p>	<p>Is only expert or only lay knowledge considered, or both? Were the participants for the case selected randomly to represent societal diversity?</p> <p>Does the case propose procedural standards, such as a protocol and/or a guidebook?</p> <p><i>To what extent does the case help innovate democratic policies, politics, or polity?</i></p> <p>Is there a comprehensive evaluation and transparent feedback procedure?</p>

A.3.1. QCA (M10) Terminological Framework

Old Binary Terms	New Terms: Quality of Outcome Performance	Quality of Scaling Potentials /Pathways	When/Where
Success	Transformative performance	Systemic uptake, lasting embedding	When innovations embed institutionally or culturally
Partial Success	Selective performance	Context-sensitive uptake, selective embedding. Serves as testing ground for future potential	When scaling works in some dimensions/contexts but not all. When pilots/replications do not embed yet, but generate insights
Mixed Success/Failure	Testing Outcome	Steppingstone for scaling potential, intermediate, cumulative contribution. Serves as testing ground for future potential	When scaling advances learning, networks, or awareness even without formal embedding. When pilots/replications do not embed yet, but generate insights
Failure	Experimental performance	Exploratory scaling, Barriers identified, lessons to be learned. Serves as testing ground for future potential	When scaling stalls but reveals structural or political obstacles. When pilots/replications do not embed yet, but generate insights

Note. This terminology seeks to make clear that no DI outcome performance and no scaling potential is wasted. Each pathway (or trajectory) is framed as part of an iterative and interactive learning-looping process towards a democratic innovation scaling ecosystem.

A.3.2. Experimental Cases: Barriers and Pitfalls

Dimensions		First dimension			
		~OUT	~IN	~HIGH	~DEEP
Interacting dimension	~OUT		REBALANCE (typical for ~IN)		KT4D (typical for ~DEEP)
	~IN	GenderQuotas (typical for ~OUT)		ITHACA (typical for ~HIGH)	
	~HIGH		REBALANCE (typical for ~IN)		KT4D (typical for ~DEEP)
	~DEEP	GenderQuotas (typical for ~OUT)		IDEal reSCUE (typical for ~HIGH)	

Note. The symbol “~” represents the absence of a condition: e.g., ~OUT is read as “the absence of scaling out potential”. In QCA terms, these are typical cases for the individual focal conjuncts, representing the combinations of the absence of scaling potentials.

A.4. Illustrations of Exemplary Combinations of Scaling Potentials

We can identify inductively promising cases by building the Knowledge Map through the case templates. We highlight four cases here, with exceptional care for the scaling potentials in the four dimensions, to be later corroborated with the QCA results. This approach allows for testing QCA findings and the solidity of the modular framework on which the case templates are built. Some of these exemplary cases include:

CIVITAS ReVeAL

This project embedded participatory planning and deliberative democratic innovations into its sustainable urban mobility pilots. Pilot city Vitoria-Gasteiz, Spain, convened stakeholder assemblies and co-creation workshops (public roundtables, online forums, neighborhood meetings, etc.) so that citizens and local stakeholders co-designed low-emission zones and street redesigns. Its success can be assessed directly on the ground by the super-block created in Vitoria-Gasteiz. It has potential for scaling HIGH, as the project's outcomes could inform policymaking at national and EU levels, promoting broader adoption of sustainable mobility practice; for scaling OUT, as the superblock model can be adapted and implemented in other cities and contexts; for scaling IN, as its insights and methodologies can be integrated into existing urban planning and transport frameworks.

Democratic Odyssey.

The project's flagship innovation is a transnational citizens' assembly of European residents, with travelling assemblies in Athens, Florence/Fiesole, and Vienna. This iterative pilot is a proof-of-concept for a permanent People's Assembly for Europe. As such, it is linked with a crowdsourced digital platform and campaign, ensuring real-time public input and broad civil society engagement in the deliberations, particularly on the involvement of citizens in poli-crises management. Its outcomes include, among others, the "planting of DO seeds" in the cities where the Assembly met; the creation of an ongoing "Citizen Council" to campaign for DO; and most noteworthy, "A Citizens' Charter to Revitalise Democracy in Europe by Navigating Future Crises Together". These outcomes are the result of DO's combination of scaling performance in four directions, namely IN (Modular Framework); OUT (translocal/transnational); DEEP (participatory Arts), and HIGH (Council of Europe, JRC, Athens, Florence, Fiesole, Vienna Municipalities, civil society networks such as European Alternatives).

DEMOCRAT

This project co-designs and pilots democratic education interventions. It uses participatory workshops to develop curricula for an EU-wide "Education for Democracy". It tests them in open, local learning projects such as school or community labs, packaging the results as a toolkit of transformative civic-education practices. It has successfully presented a comprehensive approach to enhancing democratic education across Europe. Its participatory methodology, development of competence frameworks, and pilot implementations indicate

significant progress and potential for scaling in all four dimensions, as it has developed European-level curricula and policy recommendations (scaling high), it has piloted in all EU regions (scaling out), it aims to instill democratic values and competences in learners (scaling deep), and produced a Responsible Democratic Citizenship (RDC) competence framework and a toolbox for Education for Democracy (EfD) (scaling in).

REDIRECT

The project explores experimental participatory fora to address the representative disconnect. It has organized diagnostic participatory experiments through online mini publics to explore ways to help reconnect citizens with political decision-making. However, even as it has a strong potential for scaling DEEP by addressing the underlying issues of democratic representation, its success has not yet extended to other scaling dimensions. Given that it did not establish institutional roots to replicate the experimental forums, it has not yet developed a significant guidebook or protocol for other practitioners to do so, and it lacked elite support to do either. It has to be noted that this project is still ongoing, but it demonstrates a common blind spot in democratic innovation. By not developing a roadmap to scale in all dimensions, outstanding results in a given dimension can wither in time.

The first three cases show the synergic potential of scaling dimensions for creating successful democratic innovations. In contrast, the REDIRECT case showcases the limitations of constraining them into a single scaling format. We designed the qualitative comparative analysis to identify which scaling potential configurations lead to success.

A.4.1 Scaling Out Pilots

Family of DI	EU Project (Acronym / GA)	OUT-Scope (Contexts & Boundaries)	Replicable Modules / Tools / Formats	Replication Mechanisms (How)	Key Enablers	Long-Term Pathway	Notes (evidence hints)
Administrative	CIVITAS ReVeAL — Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Livability (H2020)	City-to-city replication across EU; adaptation to differing legal & urban forms; multilingual guidance	UVAR Toolkit; regulatory packages; stakeholder engagement templates; monitoring KPIs	CIVITAS network mentoring; peer-learning labs; model by-laws and procedural roadmaps	EU guidance; city networks; demonstrator evidence; political leadership; data dashboards	Municipal incorporation into traffic by-laws; replication via national guidance & CIVITAS family	Toolkit & knowledge bank
Administrative	PentaHelix — Co-creating SECAPs (H2020)	From 8 pilots to 75+ municipalities; regional spread; cross-language materials	Five-stakeholder task-force method; SECAP co-creation templates; training kit	Regional hubs; coach-the-coaches; standardized steps and roles; repository of cases	EU Covenant of Mayors; climate policy incentives; municipal capacity	Routine inclusion of co-creation in climate/energy planning cycles; multi-level governance links	Project site; replication stats
Deliberative	EUARENAS (H2020 959420)	City pilots → transfer across municipalities (e.g., Gdansk, Reggio Emilia, Vöru)	City toolbox; mixed participatory/deliberative formats; partnership templates with CSOs/cultural hubs	Municipal partnerships; peer exchanges; adaptation manuals; public showcases	Mayor/chief officer buy-in; local CSO coalitions; cultural venues as anchors	Embedding in municipal procedures; diffusion through city networks	Project site & pilots
Deliberative	PHOENIX — Citizens' Voices for Greener Europe (HE)	Pilots replicated across FR, HU, IT, PL, GR; thematic transfer to Green Deal issues	Deliberation protocols; inclusiveness/impact evaluation framework; training materials	Partner consortium roll-outs; evaluation-led refinement; open methods for reuse	EU Green Deal agenda; civil society alliances; evaluation evidence	Adoption by municipalities/ministries and CSOs for climate policy deliberations	Project factsheets
Digital	Co-Inform — Misinformation-Resilient	Multi-country stakeholder pilots; transfer to	Browser plug-in; fact-checking dashboard;	Stakeholder training; open documentation;	Open tools; multi-stakeholder	Embedding in newsroom/public sector routines; diffusion via	CORDIS reporting

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	t Societies (H2020 770302)	newsrooms, public agencies, universities	co-creation workshop format	local champions in media & administrations	r buy-in; literacy curricula	education & CSO partners	
Digital	D-CENT — Decentralised Citizens' Engagement Tools (FP7)	City-to-city & movement-to-city transfer (Reykjavík, Barcelona, Madrid, Helsinki, etc.)	Open-source engagement platforms; e-initiative; participatory drafting; Freecoin	Open-source reuse; municipal adoption; developer & activist communities	Open licensing; strong civic tech ecosystems; political windows	Institutionalization in city platforms; spread to new cities and movements	Project archive
Digital	WeGovNow (H2020 693514)	Pilots in multiple cities (e.g., Turin, London Southwark, Berlin) with cross-context reuse	Neighborhood-level digital participation suite; co-reporting; co-decision features	City partnerships; local customization; community onboarding	Municipal service integration; user-centered design; interoperability	Sustained municipal platform use; replication through EU city networks	Project site
Direct	NEBourhoods (NEB)	Local pilots aligned with New European Bauhaus values across regions/cultures	Place-based co-design frameworks; micro-grants; community labs	Regional clusters; NEB community; design toolkits; storytelling assets	EU NEB brand; cultural institutions; local designers & NGOs	Replication via regional/municipal NEB calls and cultural anchors	NEB platform
Direct	REBALANCE (H2020)	EU-wide dialogues on transport & mobility futures; cross-country forums	Futures/visioning workshops; policy dialogues; citizen panels	Partner-hosted events; method playbooks; cross-national synthesis	EU transport policy windows; stakeholder alliances	Method reuse in transport planning & strategy	Project site
Electoral	CMCG — Citizens, Media & Conflict Governance (placeholder)	Cross-country exchange on electoral communication & conflict-sensitive participation	Guidelines for conflict-sensitive engagement; media & election dialogue formats	Training of election bodies & media councils; peer learning	Election commissions; media regulators; CSO networks	Adoption into election communication codes & protocols	To be verified with project ID
Electoral	DEMOTEC (as listed)	Transnational replication of technical-democrati	Election-adjacent civic tech; participation standards;	Open repositories; cross-border	Standardized templates; legal	Institutional uptake by EMBs/ministries; cross-country adoption	To confirm CORDIS link

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		c tools for electoral processes	observer/monitoring templates	practitioner networks	compatibility; donor support		
Participatory	CIMULACT — Citizen Visions (H2020 665948)	Pan-EU (30+ countries) → national & EU R&I programming	Visioning workshops; translation to research topics; policy synthesis templates	Transnational partner network; EC interfaces; documented methods	Commission sponsorship; high-quality synthesis; national nodes	Recurring use in EU work programs; national replication	CORDIS & project site
Participatory	EUARENAS (H2020 959420)	City-to-city diffusion via pilots and toolboxes	Participatory governance models; city toolbox; CSO partnerships	Peer exchanges; municipal networks; adaptation manuals	Political will; CSO capacity; cultural anchors	Embedding in municipal procedures; spread through networks	Project site

Note. *Scaling Out highlights cross-context replication (local → national → transnational), including cultural/linguistic transfer and city-to-city diffusion.*

A.4.2 Scaling High Pilots

Family of DI	EU Project (Acronym / GA)	High-Level Embedding Domain	Where (Political/Institutional Contexts)	How (Devices / Actions for SCA-HIGH)	Long-Term Mechanism / Pathway	Sources
Participatory / Foresight / Agenda-setting	CIMULACT — Citizen & Multi-Actor Consultation on Horizon 2020 (H2020 665948)	Institutional / Policy programming	European Commission R&I programming (H2020 → Horizon Europe); national R&I stakeholders	Citizen-derived research agendas → synthesis → inputs to EC Work Programs; guidance/templates for incorporating citizen visions	Normalization of participatory agenda-setting in EU research policy cycles (work program design; calls)	CORDIS reporting; project website (citizen visions → 23 research topics)
Administrative / Urban Governance	CIVITAS ReVeAL — Regulating Vehicle Access for Improved Livability (H2020)	Legal / Regulatory / Administrative	Municipal statutes & traffic by-laws; UVAR frameworks; national guidance links	UVAR **Toolkit & Guidance**; pilot-tested regulatory packages; model procedures and implementation playbooks for cities	Cities incorporate UVARs into binding regulations; scaling via CIVITAS network and EU guidance	Project site & Toolkit; CIVITAS knowledge bank

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Deliberative / Education Policy	DEMOCRAT — Education for Democracy (HEU)	Institutional (Education systems)	Ministries of Education; school governance; inspectorates; teacher training institutes	**Competence Framework** for Responsible Democratic Citizenship; Living Labs; curricular integration pilots; policy guidance	Framework adoption in curricula, assessment, and teacher PD standards	Project site; HE call on Education for Democracy
Analytical / Constitutional & Institutional Research	EU3D — Differentiation, Dominance & Democracy (H2020 822419)	Constitutional / Institutional	EU Treaties debate; European Parliament & Council debates; national EU coordination	Theory & scenarios of legitimate differentiation; policy options & governance models feeding institutional reforms	Use in Future of Europe debates; informing institutional design & treaty-adjacent reforms	CORDIS & project site
Administrative / Resilience Tech-Policy	IDEal reSCUE — Integrated DEsign & control of Sustainable CommUnities during Emergencies (ERC 637842)	Institutional (Emergency governance)	Civil protection agencies; municipal emergency plans; infrastructure authorities	Decision-support models & simulations → protocols for emergency planning/response; integration in SOPs	Codified procedures & planning standards inside authorities; training uptake in HEIs	CORDIS reporting
Digital & AI / Deliberative	ORBIS — AI-Augmented Deliberation (HEU)	Institutional (participation systems)	Public bodies adopting digital deliberation stacks; parliaments/cities	Socio-technical frameworks, governance rules for AI-supported participation; procurement-ready modules; standards for transparency	Institutional procurement/adoption; inclusion in participation by-laws & platform governance	Project factsheet / consortium pages
Rule of Law / Constitutional	RECONNECT — Reconciling Europe with its Citizens (H2020)	Constitutional / Legal / Institutional	EU & national rule-of-law frameworks; courts; oversight bodies	Indicators & principles; policy briefs; constitutional/legal recommendations for safeguarding democracy & fundamental rights	Incorporation into policy monitoring, parliamentary scrutiny and jurisprudential debates	Project site & CORDIS
Counter-Disinformation / Participation	REDIRECT — (HEU, project in user's ScaleDem portfolio)	Institutional / Policy	Public communication offices; regulators; civic media partnerships	Policy guidance & protocols for counter-disinformation integrated into institutional comms and consultations	Standard operating procedures; inter-agency coordination; inclusion in codes of practice	To be cross-checked with project page/CORDIS ID

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Digital Participation / Governance	SMIDGE — (HEU, project in user's ScaleDem portfolio)	Institutional / Administrative	Local/regional administrations; participation offices	Standards & toolkits for micro-participation embedded in administrative procedures & platforms	By-law updates and platform governance rules; training for officials	To be cross-checked with project page/CORDIS ID
Transnational Participation	Scalable Democracy — (initiative / project in user's portfolio)	Institutional / Constitutional (prospective)	EU & MS participation frameworks; parliamentary interfaces	Design patterns for scaling assemblies & sortition interfaces; legal adoption pathways	Inclusion in institutional participation charters & inter-level coordination rules	Concept note / design papers
AI, Media & Democracy	TITAN — (HEU project in user's portfolio)	Regulatory / Institutional	Media regulators; public broadcasters; platforms' compliance units	Standards for transparency/accountability; audit/playbooks; regulatory testbeds	Codes of conduct; procurement criteria; regulatory guidance	To be cross-checked with CORDIS ID
Global Democracy Support	WYDE — Women & Youth in Democracy (Team Europe / AFD)	Political / Institutional capacity	Partner-country institutions; electoral commissions; parliaments	Capacity-building programs; legal/policy support; inclusion mandates	Institutional capacity & legal reform packages; inter-governmental partnerships	Program page (Team Europe / AFD)
Electoral / Equality Policy	Gender Quotas — Policy instrument / EU & MS practice	Legal / Constitutional / Party rules	Constitutions; electoral laws; party statutes; funding/penalty regimes	Statutory candidate quotas; zipper lists; sanctions/incentives; oversight reporting	Hard-law entrenchment; party compliance routines; judicial review	Comparative scholarship & EU/MS legislation
Local Democratic Infrastructure	LIDD — Local Infrastructures for Deliberative Democracy (user portfolio)	Institutional / Administrative	Municipal charters; council standing orders; dedicated participation offices	Statutory citizens' panels; permanent assemblies; response duties; budget lines	By-law codification; routinised cycles; cross-city transfer via networks	Project docs / municipal statutes (to confirm)
Education / Culture & Participation	NEW DEMOCRACY (Bertelsmann Stiftung)	Institutional / Policy (soft-law)	Government consultation guidelines; civil-society standards; training systems	Toolkits; policy dialogues; model guidelines for participatory processes	Adoption into consultation manuals; accreditation/standards for practice	Program page
Digital & AI / Deliberative	MultiPoD — Multilingual & Multicultural Spaces for Political	Institutional / Platform governance	City & EU-linked deliberation platforms (e.g., Decidim); public administrations	Culture-aware AI modules; governance & transparency rules for platforms; interoperability standards	Procurement & platform policy updates; embedding in official participation portals	CORDIS facts; project site; Decidim partner posts

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	Deliberation (HEU 101178821)					
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Note. *Scaling High captures embedding in political, institutional, legal, or constitutional contexts for long-term change (rules, mandates, procedures, standards).*

A.4.3 Scaling Deep Pilots

Family of DI	EU Project (Acronym / GA)	Embedding Domain	Where (Contexts)	How (Devices / Actions)	Long-Term Mechanism / Pathway	Notes (Evidence Hints)
Deliberative / Participatory	CCINDLE – Co-Creating Inclusive Intersectional Democratic Spaces (HEU 101061256)	Emotional, Cultural, Civic, Educational	Schools & youth spaces; feminist CSOs & media networks; universities; community events	Feminist Democracy Labs; arts/narrative methods (e.g., Theatre of the Oppressed, speculative design); educator/mentor materials; co-creation with media & NGOs; campaigns	Pedagogy & facilitator capacity; diffusion via feminist/civic networks; recurring labs; publicly visible cultural outputs	CORDIS results page; project site deliverables (D6.1/D6.2)
Digital & AI / Participatory	Co-Inform – Co-Creating Misinformation-Resilient Societies (H2020 770302)	Civic, Educational	Newsrooms; public-sector comms; citizen workshops; universities	Browser plug-in & dashboards; co-creation workshops with journalists, policymakers, citizens; literacy/awareness trainings	Institutional tool uptake; media & public-sector routines; digital literacy diffusion	CORDIS reporting; IIASA project page
Deliberative / Educational / Cultural	Critical ChangeLab – Democracy meets arts (HEU 101094217)	Emotional, Cultural, Educational	Secondary schools; youth centers; arts/cultural partners; universities	Critical Change Labs; democratic pedagogy model; arts-based civic interventions; teacher/mentor	Curricular/pedagogical embedding; educator capacity; cultural anchoring via exhibits/performances	CORDIS facts/reporting; project site

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				resources; public showcases		
Administrative / Deliberative / Communications	ENCODE – Unveiling Emotional Dimensions of Politics (HEU 101132698)	Emotional, Civic, Policy	Public administrations; CSOs; media/civic communication settings; 8-country pilots	Affective pluralization framework; labs/workshops translating emotional insights to policy narratives; guidance/toolkits; mixed methods (sentiment, biometrics)	Emotion-aware policy & civic comms routines inside institutions/CSOs; spillover to civic/educational training	CORDIS facts; ENCODE site
Administrative / Resilience (tech-policy)	IDEal reSCUE – Integrated DEsign & control of Sustainable CommUNITies during Emergencies (ERC 637842)	Civic/Policy, Educational (HEIs)	Urban planning & civil protection; university labs/curricula	Agent-based simulations; decision-support models; scenario tools for emergency/resilience policy	Institutional decision routines in emergency governance; academic integration in engineering/urban planning	CORDIS reporting
Digital & AI / Deliberative	MultiPoD – Multilingual & Multicultural Spaces for Political Deliberation (HEU 101178821)	Civic, Cultural, Research/Education (HEIs)	City pilots (e.g., Athens, Brussels); civic platforms (Decidim); university research labs	Culture-Specific Language Models & Knowledge Graphs; hybrid assemblies; visual analytics; platform adoption & community co-design	Platform-level embedding; culture-aware AI modules; city/community partnerships; academic dissemination	CORDIS facts; project site; Decidim blog posts
Participatory / Civic	NEW DEMOCRACY – Program for resilient, participatory democracies (Bertelsmann Stiftung)	Civic, Policy, Educational (adult learning)	Civil society networks; policymaker dialogues; practitioner trainings	Advocacy & toolkits; convenings; integration of participatory forms into consultation & policy cycles	Norm diffusion via large networks; routinization of participatory consultation in institutions	Project description page
Deliberative / Participatory	REAL DEAL – Reshaping European Advances	Civic, Policy	Multi-country pilots; EU/MS	Participation & Deliberation Protocol;	Protocol uptake by institutions & CSOs; scaling	CORDIS facts/reporting;

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towards green Leadership
(H2020 101037071)

institutions; large
CSO networks

validated formats; joint
repository; hybrid
deliberations incl. youth
& gender-just
assemblies

through networks; repeated
use in
consultations/assemblies

European
Movement
project page

Note. Sources used for the entries: CCINDLE (results & deliverables); Critical ChangeLab (CORDIS + site); ENCODE (CORDIS + site); Co-Inform (CORDIS reporting + IIASA); IDEal reSCUE (CORDIS); MultiPoD (CORDIS + partner pages); REAL DEAL (CORDIS + European Movement); “New Democracy” program (project page).

A.4.4 Scaling In Pilots

Family of DI	Project (Acronym · duration)	Where (contexts)	How (devices / actions)	Long-term impact / change
Digital / Direct	D-CENT · 2014–2016	Cities & movements piloting open platforms	Open-source toolbox with privacy-aware auth, collaborative drafting, notifications, and collective decision modules; promotes transparent rules & equal voice online	More consistent, auditable procedures for proposals/voting; lower barriers to participate
Digital / Participatory	WeGovNow · 2016–2019	Municipal pilots (e.g., Trieste, Turin, Southwark)	Integrated “toolbox” platform for co-creation; built-in moderation & workflow to structure dialogue among citizens–CSOs–administration	Clearer participation pathways; reduced dominance by loud voices via structured tasks
Digital/AI / Information integrity	Co-Inform · 2018–2021	Co-creation labs with citizens, journalists, policymakers	Co-designed mis/disinformation tools; stakeholder co-creation method to surface blind spots; iterative usability tests	More inclusive info environments; improved critical engagement norms in deliberation
Digital/AI / Media literacy	TITAN · 2022–2025	Schools, workplaces, CSOs	AI “Socratic” coaching chatbot to scaffold critical questioning and reduce bias; pedagogy for step-by-step claim assessment	Stronger individual deliberation skills; reduced cognitive asymmetries
Deliberative / Participatory	EUARENAS · 2020–2024	Urban arenas (e.g., Vöru, Gdansk, Budapest, Reggio Emilia)	Practice-oriented pilots; toolboxes & design rules for inclusive local deliberation; attention to inclusion & governance interfaces	More even participation inside city processes; replicable facilitation standards

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Deliberative / Green transition	PHOENIX · 2022–2025	Environmental governance pilots	“Enriched Democratic Innovations”: methodology adapting CAs, PB, Débat public for inclusive green-policy deliberation; pilot diagnosis protocols	Better fit between format & context; higher deliberative quality for eco-policies
Deliberative / Green transition	REAL DEAL · 2022–2025	EU-level & multi-country assemblies (youth, gender-just)	Tested hybrid deliberation formats + online platform; common quality principles for EGD participation; guidance for institutions	More consistent standards for inclusion/fairness across countries; uptake by EU bodies
Digital / Deliberative	ORBIS · 2023–2026	Multi-scale pilots (local → EU)	Socio-technical framework + AI-enhanced tools; methodology for at-scale deliberation and co-creation; transparency & trust design	More robust, transparent online deliberation pipelines; scalable facilitation
Participatory / Youth pedagogy	Critical ChangeLab · 2023–2026	Schools & non-formal youth spaces	“Democratic pedagogy” model (Theatre of the Oppressed, speculative design) to surface marginalized voices; structured reflection loops	Deeper inclusion of youth perspectives; skills for equitable dialogue
Participatory / Inclusive design	INCITE-DEM · 2023–2026	“Democracy Labs” in 6 countries	Recruitment guidance for diverse samples; co-creation protocols; methodological guide for facilitating inclusive labs	Improved representativeness and equal voice within co-design processes
Administrative / Governance research (quality principles)	EU3D · 2019–2023	EU multilevel governance research	Legitimacy & dominance lens to diagnose power asymmetries; implications for designing fairer participatory arenas	Design criteria to avoid domination in structured dialogues
Administrative / Rule of Law & legitimacy (quality principles)	RECONNECT · 2018–2022	EU institutions & publics	Syntheses and policy guidance on engaging citizens & aligning with RoL; communication/manual for policymakers	Clearer quality benchmarks for inclusive engagement within EU processes
Cultural/Participatory (narratives)	ITHACA · 2021–2025	Migration & heritage institutions	Methods for collecting/preserving migrant narratives; participatory archiving to recognize knowledge holders	More respectful, inclusive framing → better conditions for equitable deliberation
Place-based participatory (NEB)	NEBourhoods · 2022–2025	Munich-Neuperlach lighthouse (NEB)	Co-design with residents; inclusion & beauty/sustainability criteria; iterative community sessions	Durable local norms for inclusive co-creation; clearer participation routines
Digital / Assessment standards	PERYCLES (related) · 2025–2028	Digital democracy platforms	Methods to assess platform quality; open-source reference implementations; best-practice library	Shared standards for fairness & accessibility in e-participation
Knowledge mapping / Scaling framework	SCALED · 2025–2028	Cross-project	Scaling Compass + feedback & capacity-building mechanisms to keep process quality when replicating	Codified “scaling-IN” checks during uptake and twinning

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Socio-economic / Values & mobility	REBALANCE · 2021–2024	Mobility culture & participation	Inclusive mobility values; results pack on accessibility → informs inclusive participation design in mobility fora	Better inclusion criteria and dialogue frames in mobility deliberations
Digital / Meso-aged publics & extremism (quality of discourse)	SMIDGE · 2023–2026	Online communities across 6 countries	Analysis of extremist narratives; surveys/focus groups → moderation and literacy guidance for fairer online spaces	Evidence-based safeguards for respectful, inclusive debate formats

Note. *Scaling In actions are defined as methods that strengthen the internal quality of participation—fairness, inclusion, deliberative depth. Sources: CORDIS and official project sites*